

Synthesis of 2,4-diaryl-1,5-benzodiazepines and 2,4-diaryl-2,3-dihydro-1,5-benzothiazepines

Manisha Padwad and V. N. Ingle*

Department of Chemistry, Nagpur University, Nagpur-440 010, India

Manuscript received 10 December 1997, revised 24 June 1998, accepted 16 October 1998

Various 2,4-disubstituted-1,5-benzodiazepines have been prepared by condensing 1,3-diones with *o*-phenylenediamine, and 2,4-diaryl-2,3-dihydro-1,5-benzothiazepines have been prepared by condensing hydroxychalcone and *o*-aminothiophenol in boiling dry xylene and acetic acid medium.

1,5-Benzodiazepines display various pharmacological properties¹ and have been exploited as psychopharmacological agents². It was therefore thought interesting to synthesise some new compounds of these types.

1,5-Benzodiazepine molecule shows tautomerism and can not be represented by dianil form (I) alone. Various workers suggested different structures (I)³, (II)⁴ and (III)⁵ for 1,5-benzodiazepine. In this work ir spectral data (3500–3100 cm⁻¹, NH) revealed structure (II) for 1,5-benzodiazepine.

Reactions were carried out in nitrogen atmosphere⁶ to prevent oxidation of orthophenylenediamine. In the synthesis of 2,4-diaryl-2,3-dihydro-1,5-benzothiazepines from chalcone and *o*-aminothiophenol in ethanol, formation and isolation of intermediate ketone was achieved. This ketone on treatment with methanolic acidic condition underwent

a; R = H d; R = 2-Cl
b; R = OCH₃ e; R = 3,4-O-CH₂-O-
c; R = 4-Cl f; R = 2-pyridyl

cyclodehydration to give the cyclised product, but when reactions were carried out in dry xylene products were formed in a single step without formation of any intermediate.

Experimental

M.p.s. were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. Ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 283B spectrophotometer and nmr spectra on a Varian FT-80A (200 MHz) spectrometer using TMS as an internal standard. All compounds gave satisfactory elemental analyses.

1,5-Benzodiazepines were prepared from β -diketones, the latter being prepared by alkaline hydrolysis of chalcone dibromide⁷.

2-(4-Hydroxyphenyl)-4-phenyl-1,5-benzodiazepine (**1a**) : A mixture of 1,3-dione (0.01 mol), ethanol (20 ml) and glacial acetic acid (0.5 ml) was refluxed in nitrogen atmosphere on a water-bath for 12 h. The mixture was then cooled and the solid formed was crystallised from ethanol to give **1a** (60%), m.p. 205°, ν_{\max} (KBr) 3385 (NH), 3187 (OH), 1631 (CN), 1589 (NH), 1457 (aromatic ring breathing), 1273 (COC); δ (CDCl₃ + DMSO-d₆) 6.5–6.6 (14H, ArH), 7.6 (1H, NH), O-H offscale. Similarly, other compounds were prepared : **1b** (59%), m.p. 135°; **c** (58%),

213°; **d** (55%), 126°; **e** (45%), 236°, ν_{\max} (KBr) 3377 br (NH and OH), 1588 (NH), 1578 (CN), 1445 (aromatic ring breathing), 1312 (CN), 1254 (COC), δ (CDCl₃ + DMSO-d₆) 5.95 (2H, OCH₂O), 6.7–7.9 (11H, ArH), 7.6 (1H, C₃H), 9.5 (1H, NH); **f** (61%), 328°.

1,5-Benzothiazepines were prepared from chalcones by usual methods.

2-(4-Methoxyphenyl)-4-(4-hydroxyphenyl)-2,3-dihydro-1,5-benzothiazepine (2b): A mixture of 4'-hydroxy-4-methoxybenzalacetophenone (0.01 mol), *o*-aminothiophenol (0.012 mol), dry xylene (20 ml) and glacial acetic acid (0.5 ml) was refluxed for 4 h. The colour of reaction changed from light yellow to dark yellow. On cooling, the solid formed was crystallised from methanol to give **2b** (59%), m.p. 173°; ν_{\max} 3132 (OH), 1603 (CN), 1443 (aromatic ring breathing), 1221 (COC), 1171 (CS), 762 (CS), 691 (CSC); δ (CDCl₃ + DMSO-d₆) 2.8–3.0 (2H, CH₂), 3.8 (1H, OCH₃), 5.0 (1H, C₂-H), 6.8–7.9 (12H, ArH), 9.75 (1H, OH). Similarly, other compounds were prepared: **2a** (58%), m.p. 190°; **c** (61%), 233°; **d** (56%),

234°; **c** (65%), 195°; **f** (59%), 205°.

References

1. M. Di Braccio, G. Roma, G. C. Grossi, G. Leoncini and M. Maresca, *Farmaco*, 1992, **47**, 77 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1992, **116**, 235593); P. Chinchkhede, Ph.D. Thesis, Nagpur University, 1991; V. K. Srivastava, R. K. Satsangi and K. Kishore, *Arzenim-Forsch.*, 1982, **32**, 1512; S. U. Kulkarni and K. A. Thakar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, **53**, 279.
2. U. C. Pant, B. S. Gaur and M. Chugh, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1988, **27**, 752, and references cited therein.
3. J. Thiele and G. Steimmig, *Chem. Ber.*, 1907, **40**, 935; J. A. Baltrop, C. G. Richards, D. M. Russel and G. Rybake, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 1132; I. L. Finar, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 4094.
4. S. B. Vaisman, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1940, **34**, 5847; 1944, **38**, 750.
5. D. Lloyd and D. R. Marshall, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 2597; W. J. Barry, I. L. Finar and E. F. Mooney, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1965, **21**, 1095.
6. A. I. Vogel, "Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry", 4th. ed., Longmans, London, 1980.
7. S. U. Kulkarni and K. A. Thakar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, **52**, 850.